

The development of tourism through "Abu-l Mu'in an-Nasafi" scientific research center

Urolov Ghaybulla

Free researcher of Karshi state university

Key words: Cultural monuments, Nasaf-Kaziri, scientific research center, tafsir, hadith, aqeed, fiqh, kalam, philosophy, ancient manuscripts, Islamic studies.

Abstract: In this article, in the years of independence based on the increasing attention to cultural heritage, including the establishment of the Abu-l Mu'in al-Nasafi scientific-research center in Kashkadarya, the goals and tasks of the center and the development of the tourism industry in the region were considered.

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022 "On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026" No. PF-60[1], as well as the Decree of the head of our country dated May 24, 2017 "On further development of the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources" Resolution PQ-2995 dated May 24, 2017 "On measures to further improve the system of preservation, research and promotion of ancient written sources", dated June 20, 2017 "Regarding Uzbekistan under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of a center for the study of cultural monuments abroad" dated July 23, 2018 "On measures to establish a center of Islamic civilization in Uzbekistan under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated March 26, 2021 "Measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational affairs" "about". In their decisions our ancestors, the idea of scientific spiritual preservation and development left by it is planned to bring its quality to the ranks of the advanced countries of the world. On October 11, 2021, with in a meeting with the voters of Kashkadarya, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan established the Abu Muin Nasafi Scientific and Research Center (Nasafi Center) under the Karshi State University, and instructed about the task of collecting and in-depth study of the heritage of about 400 mature scholars who were born and raised in the oasis in one place. given Also, Bazdavis who grew up in our yut, in Nasaf-karshi[2] oasis. The heritage of Kasbawis and Subahis is also being researched.

Kashkadarya oasis has an ancient history[3:1492-1495]. Cities and villages were built in this country in the centuries before Christ. In 2002 and 2006, the 2700th anniversaries of the cities of Shahrisabz and Karshi were celebrated. Undoubtedly, the people of science and creativity have contributed to the global expansion of these cities. the contribution of heritage is great [4:135-138], science and social spheres are highly

developed in this area. There is a lot of information about this in ancient writings. One of the medieval Arab historians, Abdulkarim Sam'ani, in his work "Genealogy" ("Al-Ansab"), says that resistance scholars and writers also used the nickname "Madani" [5:1-6], the word "Madina" has eight states that it is attributed to the city. They are: Madinai Munawwara, Baghdad, Isfahan, Nishapur, inner fortress in Marv, Bukhara, Samarkand and Nasaf cities. Some Nasaf scholars, including T. Yashilyurt, say that scholars from Muslim countries [6:96-100] came to Nasaf, Samarkand and Bukhara to acquire intellectual knowledge such as tafsir, hadith, aqeed, fiqh, kalam and philosophy. But in ancient Nasaf and Kesh, literature and art also developed at a high level [7:121-123]. There are many evidences [8:128-131] that the scientific conference of jurisprudents - "Majlisi al-Tadris" was held here as early as the 10th century, and the Meccan scholar Abul Qasim Ka'bai participated in it. According to historian Sam'ani, there was a special center of enlightenment built for people of knowledge in Nasaf, and its name was "Al-Qallos" (House of Scholars). This evidence alone shows the role of people of knowledge and culture here. Nevertheless, the sources related to them have not been studied until now;

who is engaged in the collection, study and promotion of oasis scientific [9:128-132] and literary sources at the university, has adequate conditions for conducting scientific and practical research, and translates sources in eastern languages [10:73-76] the lack of a system with mechanisms for creating special works about them;

There is a high level of interest in the scientific and literary [11] sources of the Kashkadarya oasis in the world, and although some of them are used as basic textbooks and manuals in Islamic higher education institutions, their authors have no idea about the country and the people they brought up [12:59-63]. The existence of the need to introduce the country's name and intellectual potential to the world through the names of famous scholars;

Karshi State University and other universities in the republic despite the fact that among the professors and teachers of educational institutions, researches on the heritage of scientists and writers who grew up in the region were carried out to a certain extent, they did not take a systematic form. The group of scientists to be formed in the center, as well as the need to organize the scientific activities of qualified experts interested in the research of a large number of hitherto unexplored sources [13:386-391];

Scientific and methodological foundations of the fight against the ideas of harmful currents have been created in the work of classical scholars [14:292-296]. There is still a need for such literature in modern Islamic studies;

paucity of intellectual centers working on the basis of original sources, which help to arm the specialists working in the history of the country and spiritual and educational structures [15:26-28];

In 2021, under the leadership of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh.M. Mirziyoev, based on the interruption of activity in the following [16:86-90] years and the satisfaction of the effort to restore it, regarding the introduction of old manuscripts into scientific use, which remain unused and neglected among the population, as a result of which the quality of reading and the possibility of use are lost. In paragraph 2 of the minutes of the meeting No. 34 held on June 16, a task was given to establish scientific research centers at the departments of each specialty and to create all the conditions for them to earn income. Order No. 314 of July 23 was issued. In order to ensure the execution of this order: "Abu-l Mu'in an-Nasafi" research center of Karshi State University was established.

The purpose of the establishment of the center:

- Spiritual and educational measures implemented in the Republic contribute to the improvement of the effectiveness of activities;
- our ancestors kept in various foundations and private treasures
- to create an opportunity to identify, collect, study and promote the sources of scientific and literary heritage; purely for work in the field of religious enlightenment in the country
- to support the development of scientific and methodical bases of belief, freedom of will;
- It was determined to help the development of intellectual potential at the university.

Used literature

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022 йил 28 январдаги ПФ-60-сон “Янги Ўзбекистоннинг 2022–2026 йилларга мўлжалланган тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида” ги Фармони.
2. Хасанов А. Қашқадарё воҳаси шаҳарсозлиги ва меъморчилиги (XVI – XIX асрлар). – Тошкент: Ворис нашриёти, 2019.
3. Hasanov, A. (2020). Kesh-Shakhrisabz oasis in the middle ages. International Journal of Advanced Science and Technology, 29(5), 1492-1495.
4. Khudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Guzar’s ethymology in Historical Sources. International Journal of Development and Public Policy, 2(3), 135-138.

5. Muminovich, H. A. (2022). TERRITORIAL AND GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF THE CITIES OF THE TERMIZ OASIS IN THE EARLY MIDDLE AGES. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 6, 1-6.
6. Khasanov, A. M. (2021). Historical and Geographical Regions of Chaghaniyan. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(4), 96-100
7. Karimov, B. (2021). Historical Geography of Yakkabog District. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(4), 121-123.
8. Xudaykulovich, E. A. (2022). Handicraft and Trade in Guzar District. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(8), 128-131.
9. Eshov, B. J., & Hasanov, A. M. (2016). CERTAIN REASONINGS ABOUT ANCIENT LOCAL POPULATION AND THE NOMADIC OF CENTRAL ASIA. *Education Transformation Issues*, (1), 128-132.
10. Muminov, U. (2021). Historical Gates of Karshi. *International Journal of Development and Public Policy*, 1(6), 73-76.
11. Xudoyqulovich, B. K. D. E. A. (2021). HISTORICAL GEOGRAPHICAL CLASSIFICATION AND ECONOMIC, SOCIO-POLITICAL CLASSIFICATION OF THE GUZAR DEPARTMENT IN THE SECOND HALF OF THE XIX CENTURY CONDITION. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government Vol*, 27(5).
12. Bahrom, K. (2022). SOCIO-ECONOMIC LIFE AND ADMINISTRATIVE TERRITORY OF SHAKHRISABZ PRINCIPALITY IN THE 19TH CENTURY. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(09), 59-63.
13. Мўминов, У. (2023). THE ROLE OF THE CITY OF KARSHI IN FOREIGN TRADE. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 2(14), 386-391.
14. Khudoykulovich, E. A. (2023). ISSUES OF THE HISTORICAL-GEOGRAPHICAL LOCATION OF GUZAR DISTRICT. *JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS IN SCIENTIFIC AND EDUCATIONAL RESEARCH*, 2(14), 292-296.
15. Matluba, R. (2022). THE ROLE OF THE HISTORICAL MONUMENTS OF THE KASHKADARYA OASIS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. *Spectrum Journal of Innovation, Reforms and Development*, 6, 26-28.
16. Bahrom, K. (2022). Political-Administrative Territory of The City of Karshi in The Second Half of The 19th Century-The Beginning of The 20th Century. *International Journal of Scientific Trends*, 1(2), 86-90.

